

Establishment of Relations between Complex Stability and Phosphate Group Basicity for the Copper(II) Complexes of Simple Phosphate Monoesters in Dioxane-Water Mixtures

M. CLARA F. MAGALHÃES** and HELMUT SIGEL*

Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Basel, Spitalstrasse 51, CH-4056 Basel, Switzerland

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The acidity constants of $H(R-MP)^-$, where $R-MP^{2-}$ = 4-nitrophenyl phosphate ($NPhP^{2-}$), phenyl phosphate (PhP^{2-}), D-ribose 5'-monophosphate ($RibMP^{2-}$), and n-butyl phosphate (BuP^{2-}) and the stability constants of the corresponding binary $Cu(R-MP)$ complexes were collected for aqueous solution and for 20, 30, 40 and 50% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures ($I=0.1 M$, $NaNO_3$; 25°). For each solvent $\log K_{Cu(R-MP)}^{Cu}$ versus $pK_{H(R-MP)}^H$ plots were constructed; in all cases straight lines are obtained. The corresponding straight-line equations (determined via a least-squares procedure) together with the pK_a value of a given phosphate group allow now to predict the stability of the corresponding $Cu(R-MP)$ complex in the considered solvent.

Phosphate groups are important binding sites for metal ions in biological systems, as is evident from their occurrence, e.g. in nucleic acids, as well as in nucleotides which are substrates for many metal ion-dependent enzymic reactions. Therefore, metal ion-phosphate complexes have been studied in some detail¹, but most stability constants available refer to aqueous solution^{2,3}. However, in an active site cavity of an enzyme one has to expect that the 'effective' or 'equivalent solution' dielectric constant is reduced compared to the situation in bulk water⁴⁻⁶. With this in mind we studied now the influence of a decreasing solvent polarity on the stability of Cu^{2+} complexes of simple phosphate monoesters by applying various 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures as solvents.

It is one of the aims of the present study to facilitate the development of a sense for the size of the effects connected with a decreasing solvent polarity. Therefore, stability constants of the Cu^{2+} complexes of 4-nitrophenyl phosphate ($NPhP^{2-}$), phenyl phosphate (PhP^{2-}), D-ribose 5'-monophosphate ($RibMP^{2-}$), and n-butyl phosphate (BuP^{2-}) are compared for aqueous solution, and for 20, 30, 40 and 50% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures. The stability constants of the corresponding complexes in aqueous solution have been determined earlier⁷, and those of the Cu^{2+} complexes of $NPhP^{2-}$, PhP^{2-} , and $RibMP^{2-}$ in the mentioned solvents are also known⁸. The equilibrium data for the Cu^{2+}/BuP^{2-} systems have now been determined. Combination of all these results allows for each of the mentioned solvents to establish the relation between complex stability and phosphate group basicity.

Results and Discussion

Definition of the equilibrium constants: Simple phosphate monoesters ($R-MP^{2-}$) are dibasic species

which may carry two protons at their phosphate group. However, the release of the first proton from monoesterified derivatives of phosphoric acid, i.e. from $H_2(R-MP)$ species, occurs at low pH; for example, the first proton from diprotonated uridine 5'-monophosphate, $H_2(UMP)$, is released in aqueous solution⁷ with $pK_{H_2(UMP)}^H = 0.7 \pm 0.3$ and in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water⁹ with $pK_{H_2(UMP)}^H = 2.27 \pm 0.05$ ($I=0.1 M NaNO_3$; 25°).

Indeed, the first proton from the phosphoric acid residue in $H_2(R-MP)$ is completely released before deprotonation of $H(R-MP)^-$ and complex formation between Cu^{2+} and $R-MP^{2-}$ occurs. The experimental data of the potentiometric pH titrations for all the systems and solvents considered here may be completely described by the following two equilibria,

$$K_{H(R-MP)}^H = [R-MP^{2-}][H^+]/[H(R-MP)^-] \quad (1b)$$

$$K_{Cu(R-MP)}^{Cu} = [Cu(R-MP)]/([Cu^{2+}][R-MP^{2-}]) \quad (2b)$$

Cu^{2+}/n -butyl phosphate system: Regarding the Cu^{2+} complexes of n-butyl phosphate (BuP^{2-}) the determination of the stability constant, $K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}$, was straight forward in water⁷ as well as in the water mixtures containing 20, 30, or 40% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane. However, in solutions of 50% (v/v) dioxane-water the procedure was hampered by Cu^{2+} hydrolysis, i.e. the formation of hydroxo-complexes, but an estimation could still be achieved: $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu} = 4.83 \pm 0.08$.

To obtain a solid basis also for this value the results valid for water and for water mixtures with 20, 30, and 40% (v/v) dioxane were plotted (Fig. 1).

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Fig. 1. Relationship between $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}$ and $pK_{H(BuP)}^H$ for the $Cu(BuP)$ complex as it results from the addition of increasing amounts of 1,4-dioxane to the aqueous solution of the components ($I=0.1 M$, $NaNO_3$; 25°) (see Table 1). The data points 1 to 4 refer to the solvents: (1) water, and water containing (2) 20%, (3) 30% and (4) 40% (v/v) dioxane. The least-squares line is drawn according to equation (3). The intercept of the vertical arrow ($=pK_{H(BuP)}^H$ in 50% dioxane) with the regression line in the upper right-hand corner of the figure gives $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}=4.83$ for the stability of the $Cu(BuP)$ complex in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water (see also text).

It is evident that the plot $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}$ vs $pK_{H(BuP)}^H$ yields a perfect straight line, as one would expect¹⁰, for which the following equation holds (least-squares regression line; the error limits correspond to 1σ ; the correlation coefficient $R=0.9997$):

$$\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu} = (1.238 \pm 0.022) \times pK_{H(BuP)}^H - (5.202 \pm 0.159) \quad (3)$$

With equation (3) and $pK_{H(BuP)}^H=8.10$, valid for 50% (v/v) dioxane-water, $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}=4.83 \pm 0.03$ is obtained, in perfect agreement with the above estimation.

Relations between complex stability and phosphate group basicity in several solvents: The available acidity constants of the $H(R-MP)^-$ species and the stability constants of the corresponding $Cu(R-MP)$ complexes are listed in Table 1, together with some

details on the solvent mixtures¹¹⁻¹³. From these results it is immediately evident that in all cases $pK_{H(R-MP)}^H$ of the $H(R-MP)^-$ species and $\log K_{Cu(R-MP)}^{Cu}$ of the $Cu(R-MP)$ complexes increase considerably with increasing amounts of dioxane present in the aqueous solvent mixtures (see also Fig. 1). It is thus clear⁸ that a decreasing polarity resulting from the increasing amounts of organic solvent favours the affinity of negatively charged species for protons and metal ions; i.e., the interaction between oppositely charged ions is favoured in agreement with earlier observations^{4,14}.

However, more important is the following question. Is there a correlation between complex stability and phosphate group basicity in the several

TABLE 1—NEGATIVE LOGARITHMS OF ACIDITY CONSTANTS OF SEVERAL $H(R-MP)^-$ SPECIES (EQN. 1) AND LOGARITHMS OF THE CORRESPONDING $Cu(R-MP)$ COMPLEXES (EQN. 2)

In dependence on the amount of dioxane added to water and on the resulting dielectric constant ($I=0.1 M$, $NaNO_3$, 25°)*

R-MP ²⁻	Dioxane % (v/v)	Mol fraction	ϵ^{**}	$pK_{H(R-MP)}^H$	$\log K_{Cu(R-MP)}^{Cu}$
NPhP ²⁻	0	0	78.5	5.05 ± 0.01	2.93 ± 0.04
	20	0.050	61.3	5.70 ± 0.01	2.90 ± 0.01
	30	0.083	52.7	6.01 ± 0.01	3.27 ± 0.01
	40	0.124	44.1	6.34 ± 0.01	3.63 ± 0.01
	50	0.175	35.2	6.63 ± 0.01	3.99 ± 0.02
PhP ²⁻	0	0	78.5	5.85 ± 0.01	2.77 ± 0.01
	20	0.050	61.3	6.46 ± 0.01	3.35 ± 0.01
	30	0.083	52.7	6.78 ± 0.01	3.72 ± 0.01
	40	0.124	44.1	7.11 ± 0.01	4.12 ± 0.02
	50	0.175	35.2	7.38 ± 0.01	4.40 ± 0.03
RibMP ²⁻	0	0	78.5	6.24 ± 0.01	2.96 ± 0.02
	20	0.050	61.3	6.70 ± 0.01	3.45 ± 0.01
	30	0.083	52.7	6.93 ± 0.01	3.77 ± 0.02
	40	0.124	44.1	7.19 ± 0.01	4.09 ± 0.03
	50	0.175	35.2	7.38 ± 0.01	4.38 ± 0.05
BuP ²⁻	0	0	78.5	6.72 ± 0.02	3.12 ± 0.06
	20	0.050	61.3	7.26 ± 0.02	3.80 ± 0.02
	30	0.083	52.7	7.56 ± 0.01	4.14 ± 0.03
	40	0.124	44.1	7.85 ± 0.01	4.53 ± 0.05
	50	0.175	35.2	8.10 ± 0.01	4.83 ± 0.03^a

*The errors given are three times the standard error of the mean value or the sum of the probable systematic errors, whichever is larger. The equilibrium constants valid for aqueous solutions⁷ are from our earlier work, as are the values for the NPhP, PhP, and RibMP systems in the dioxane-water mixtures⁹.

**The dielectric constants for the dioxane-water mixtures are interpolated from the data given in Refs. 11-13.

^aThis value was obtained from a $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}$ vs $pK_{H(BuP)}^H$ plot by using the values measured in water and in water mixtures containing 20, 30 or 40% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane and by extrapolating towards $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}$ with the experimentally determined $pK_{H(BuP)}^H$ value for 50% (v/v) dioxane-water (see Fig. 1). The potentiometric pH-titrations were hampered by Cu^{2+} hydrolysis but the estimate from four titrations (an evaluation was possible only for two pH values in each case) gave $\log K_{Cu(BuP)}^{Cu}=4.83 \pm 0.08$ in perfect agreement with the above value (see text).

solvents? In other words, is there a linear relationship between $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}}^{\text{H}}$, as is known¹⁰ from other series of structurally related ligands? Indeed, this is the case as is evident from Fig. 2, where the corresponding equilibrium constants (Table 1) are plotted for the systems in water and water containing 20, 30, 40, or 50% (v/v) dioxane. It is clear that for a given solvent the data for 4-nitrophenyl phosphate (NPhP^{2-}), phenyl phosphate (PhP^{2-}) and n-butyl phosphate (BuP^{2-}) fit within experimental error on a straight line (Fig. 2). Furthermore, the value for D-ribose 5'-monophosphate (RibMP^{2-}) fits also on this line, showing that RibMP^{2-} behaves like a simple phosphate monoester with a noncoordinating organic residue.

Fig. 2. Relationship between $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}}^{\text{H}}$ for the Cu^{2+} 1:1 complexes of NPhP^{2-} , PhP^{2-} , RibMP^{2-} and BuP^{2-} (always from left to right) in water and in water containing 20, 30, 40 or 50% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane. The least-squares lines are drawn in each case through the corresponding four data sets (see Table 1); the equations for these reference lines are given in Table 2 (entry nos. 1b-5). All plotted equilibrium constants refer to solutions at 25° and $I=0.1 M$ (NaNO_3).

Despite the described normal behaviour of RibMP it is interesting to observe that there is still something special. In aqueous solution the value for $\text{p}K_{\text{H(RibMP)}}^{\text{H}}$ is larger by 0.4 $\text{p}K$ unit than that for $\text{p}K_{\text{H(PhP)}}^{\text{H}}$, while in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water the acidity constants of H(RibMP)^- and H(PhP)^- are identical within experimental error (Table 1 and Fig. 2). This means that the basicity of the phosphate residue of RibMP^{2-} is less affected by the presence of dioxane molecules in the solvent than that of PhP^{2-} . An explanation of this observation, which is similar to a previous one⁸, could be that the hydrophilic ribose residue due to its OH groups attracts so many water molecules that a local

increase in the effective dielectric constant occurs; in other words, the dioxane concentration close to RibMP is lower than it is in the bulk solvent-mixture. Of course, for PhP^{2-} due to the hydrophobic nature of the phenyl ring just the opposite is true. Needless to emphasise that the stabilities of Cu(RibMP) and Cu(PhP) still reflect exactly the basicities of RibMP^{2-} and PhP^{2-} as is evident from Fig. 2 and Table 1.

Construction of reference-line (or base-line) plots of $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ vs $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}}^{\text{H}}$ in several solvents: Least-square calculations for the five straight lines shown in Fig. 2, give the slopes (m) and intercepts (b) summarised in Table 2. Several conclusions are evident. (i) Most important is that the use of these straight-line equations allows calculation of $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$, i.e. of the complex stability of Cu(R-MP) , for any phosphate ligand with a known

TABLE 2—CORRELATIONS BETWEEN Cu^{2+} -PHOSPHATE COMPLEX STABILITY AND PHOSPHATE GROUP BASICITY FOR SEVERAL DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Slopes (m) and intercepts (b) for the straight-baseline plots $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ vs $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}}^{\text{H}}$ as calculated by the least-squares procedure from the experimental equilibrium constants given in Table 1 for NPhP , PhP , RibMP and BuP ($I=0.1 M$, NaNO_3 ; 25°)*

No.	Dioxane % (v/v)	m	b	R^{**}
1a ^a	0	0.453 ± 0.056	0.055 ± 0.340	0.971
1b	0	0.481 ± 0.037	-0.072 ± 0.221	0.994
2	20	0.573 ± 0.018	-0.364 ± 0.115	0.999
3	30	0.559 ± 0.015	-0.089 ± 0.106	0.999
4	40	0.593 ± 0.037	-0.181 ± 0.261	0.996
5	50	0.571 ± 0.022	0.190 ± 0.160	0.999

*Straight-line equation, $y=mx+b$, where x represents the $\text{p}K_a$ value of any phosphate monoester and y the calculated $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ value of the corresponding Cu(R-MP) complex; the errors given with m and b correspond to one standard deviation (1σ).

**Correlation coefficient.

^aEntry no. 1a is from Tables V and VI of Ref. 7 and refers also to an aqueous solution at 25° with $I=0.1 M$ (NaNO_3).

$\text{p}K_a$ value in any of the solvents listed. (ii) The straight-line parameters obtained now for the $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}}^{\text{Cu}}$ vs $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}}^{\text{H}}$ plot for an aqueous solution are within one standard deviation identical with a previous evaluation⁷. (iii) The slopes (m) of the straight lines agree within two standard deviations for all five solvents. (iv) In fact, the average of the slopes for entries 1b through 5 in Table 2, results in $m=0.555 \pm 0.019$ (1σ); this value is within two standard deviations identical with the individual slopes and it allows the conclusion that within the experimental error limits the five straight lines are parallel. (v) The last point may be helpful for estimations of stability constants of phosphate complexes, because the same may to a first approximation also be surmised for phosphate complexes of other metal ions.

Table 3 lists the deviations from the least-squares lines for each complex of the four phosphate ligands considered in the five different solvents. To provide a reliable error limit for any stability constant

TABLE 3—LOGARITHMIC DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE EXPERIMENTAL STABILITY CONSTANTS ($\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}^{\text{Cu}}}$; TABLE 1) FOR THE Cu^{2+} COMPLEXES WITH NPhP^{2-} , PhP^{2-} , RibMP^{2-} AND BuP^{2-} AND THE LEAST-SQUARES LINES OF $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}^{\text{Cu}}}$ VS $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}^{\text{H}}}$ PLOTS AS DETERMINED BY THE FOUR COMPLEX SYSTEMS AVAILABLE FOR EACH OF THE FIVE DIFFERENT SOLVENTS (TABLE 2)*
No. Dioxane Cu(NPhP) Cu(PhP) Cu(RibMP) Cu(BuP) SD*
% (v/v)

1b ^a	0	-0.03	0.03	0.03	-0.04	0.019
2	20	0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.01	0.009
3	30	0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.00	0.008
4	40	0.00	0.04	-0.04	0.01	0.017
5	50	0.01	0.00	-0.02	0.01	0.01

*The farthest column to the right gives the standard deviation (SD) resulting from the listed differences.

^aFor entry no. 1a of Table 2, SD=0.026 (Ref. 7).

calculated with the equations of Table 2 and a given $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ value, for each solvent the standard deviation of the four data points from the least-squares line was calculated; the corresponding values are given in Table 3 in the column at the far right.

Users of the results described in this section are recommended to apply the equations of Table 2 for phosphate ligands with a $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ value within the approximate $\text{p}K_{\text{H(R-MP)}^{\text{H}}}$ range covered by the ligands considered now (Table 1), and to use as the error limits of the calculated stability constant $\log K_{\text{Cu(R-MP)}^{\text{Cu}}}$ three times the standard deviation given in Table 3 for the corresponding solvent system. We ourselves intend to apply this procedure for a more detailed study of the solvent-dependent metal ion-nucleic base recognition of adenosine monophosphate (AMP^{2-}) complexes¹⁵, and also to the question whether the carboxylate group in orotidinate 5'-monophosphate (OMP^{3-}) complexes^{9,16} participates in the binding of metal ions in $\text{M}(\text{OMP})^-$ complexes or not.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared with distilled and CO_2 -free water. 1,4-Dioxane (extra pure, Merck) was used. All the other reagents including n-butyl phosphate were the same as used before⁷.

Determination of equilibrium constants: The potentiometric pH titrations were carried out with a Metrohm equipment^{7,8} using a 6.0202.100 (JC) macro glass electrode. The direct pH-meter readings were used in the calculations for the acidity constants; no 'corrections' were applied for the change in solvent from water to the dioxane-water mixtures, though correction factors have been

published^{17,18}. The connected aspects have been discussed elsewhere^{6,19}.

The acidity constants, $K_{\text{H(BuP)}^{\text{H}}}$, of $\text{H}(\text{BuP})^-$ (where $\text{BuP}^{2-} = n$ -butyl phosphate) and the stability constants, $K_{\text{Cu(BuP)}^{\text{Cu}}}$, of the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{BuP})$ complex in the several solvents were determined exactly as described earlier⁷; this includes the concentration of the reactants, as well as the calculation procedures. This means that 50 ml of 0.54 mM HNO_3 and NaNO_3 ($I=0.1 M$; 25°) in the presence and absence of 0.3 mM BuP^{2-} were titrated under N_2 with 1 ml of 0.03 M NaOH ; the corresponding $K_{\text{H(BuP)}^{\text{H}}}$ values were calculated for the several solvent mixtures from at least four independent pairs of titrations within the pH range determined by $\text{p}K_{\text{H(BuP)}^{\text{H}}} \pm 1.6$ and by taking into account the species H^+ , $\text{H}(\text{BuP})^-$ and BuP^{2-} .

The conditions for the determination of the stability constants, $K_{\text{Cu(BuP)}^{\text{Cu}}}$, of the $\text{Cu}(\text{BuP})$ complex ($I=0.1 M$, NaNO_3 ; 25°) were the same as given above for the acidity constant (also Ref. 7), but NaNO_3 was partly replaced by 1.67 and 3.33 mM $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, i.e. the BuP to Cu^{2+} ratios were 1:5.6 and 1:11. The stability constant was computed by taking into account the species H^+ , $\text{H}(\text{BuP})^-$, BuP^{2-} , Cu^{2+} and $\text{Cu}(\text{BuP})$; the data were collected from about 5% complex formation to the beginning of the hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} , which was evident from the titrations without BuP^{2-} . The individually calculated values for $\log K_{\text{Cu(BuP)}^{\text{Cu}}}$ showed no dependence on pH or on the excess of Cu^{2+} . For all systems at least four, in fact usually six, independent pairs of titration curves were recorded and the results averaged.

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